

Scientific and Theoretical Foundations for Organizing Independent Activities of Students through the Development of Media Literacy

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Abstract:

This article describes the current state and issues related to the organization of independent activities for university students, the scientific and theoretical foundations of organizing independent activities, and the features of media literacy in the professional activities of students.

Keywords: media, literacy, media literacy, media education, media competence, pedagogy.

Worldwide, special attention is being paid to the use of information and communication technologies in professional education, the modernization of vocational training, the adaptation of educational programs to the needs of the digital environment, and the development of information competencies for future specialists. In five laws on media and information literacy adopted by UNESCO (the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) in 2018, it is stated that media and information literacy is one of the competencies necessary for education, life, and work today, and it is given special importance. Based on this, it is essential to organize independent activities in education through the development of media literacy among students.

Based on the educational experiences of countries leading in the Global Information and Communication Technology Development Index (ICT Development Index), media tools are widely used in the process of professional education and play an important role in organizing the independent activities of future specialists. In higher education, it is especially important to substantively develop the educational and methodological support for organizing independent activities by enhancing students' media literacy, modeling preparation for independent work, and improving the methodology for organizing independent activities through the development of motivational, personal, informational, and activity-oriented aspects of students' media literacy.

From this perspective, it is essential to develop in students special qualities, personal and professional competencies, media literacy, media competence, and readiness for independent activities in education [2].

In our country, special attention is given to organizing the process of professional education in line with contemporary requirements, including the integration of information and communication technologies into the professional education system and the preparation of highly qualified personnel. In the development strategy for the seven priority areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the primary tasks include 'transferring the systematic engagement in professional education to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations in full, doubling the volume of vocational training, and providing vocational training for a total of 1 million unemployed citizens'¹.

In this regard, a methodology is being developed in education for preparing future specialists for professional activities, as well as a methodology for assessing the qualities inherent to their specialty and their level of readiness for independent work. The application of advanced methodologies and technologies in the process of professional education creates ample opportunities for enhancing students' media literacy and their practical preparation for independent activities.

In our republic, as the methodology for preparing students for professional pedagogical activities is improved based on innovative approaches, the digital educational environment demands practical application and development of media literacy knowledge.

A distinctive feature of building a digital educational environment is the implementation and use of digital technologies, most of which have the following didactic characteristics: freedom to search for various information on the global network; interactivity (ensuring wide use of information in the learning process); multimedia (comprehensive use of various sources when obtaining information); hyper-reactivity (free navigation through the text). To build this environment, it is necessary to modernize the system of professional education, implement educational programs in accordance with the needs of the digital environment, widely integrate digital technologies into the educational process of educational institutions, and develop professional information competencies in preparation for professional activities.

The digital educational environment is the process of developing modern ICT tools aimed at achieving the psychological and pedagogical goals of education and ensuring their methodology and practice for optimal use. The main factor in developing students' skills for organizing independent activities is teaching them the correct and independent use of educational resources, as well as library and information technologies in the digital educational environment. Taking these factors into account, it is necessary to integrate information technologies and media tools into the professional education system and to enhance the media literacy of learners. In carrying out independent activities based on media knowledge, the following tasks are addressed: improving the education system aimed at preparing qualified specialists capable of independently performing professional functional tasks; guidance on the development of professionals' competencies; creating education based on modern technologies and information resources, and enhancing the quality of personnel training.

It is important to distinguish between the goals and objectives of the concepts 'independent learning,' 'independent activity,' and 'independent work,' which are closely related in content and essence. Independent work serves as a means of reinforcing students' theoretical and practical knowledge; independent learning is the educational process that allows learners to achieve

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026.' Collection of Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2022. - p. 39

educational goals and develop their established professional competencies; independent activity embodies both professional and personal motives for acquiring new knowledge throughout life, continuous self-improvement, and a creative approach.

Independent activity is a learning activity aimed at the independent and creative execution of educational tasks by learners in a given subject. The foundation of independent activity is independent work. Independent activity defines the student's autonomy in professional activities.

The motivational, cognitive, practical-activity, and creative components of regulating and developing independent activity in the professional education system are crucial factors in organizing independent educational and cognitive activities when preparing learners for their profession and for self-directed learning. It is precisely independent learning activities that guide students toward self-work and the execution of independent tasks from the perspectives of theoretical, practical, and autonomous study [4].

Modern developments in the field of information technologies, new digital systems, and the evolution of the media and information environment categorize literacy into the following types (see Figure 1), which are implemented in stages.

Figure 1. Types and Description of Literacy

The components of an information society, based on modern information and communication technology, are the mass media. 'Media' comes from the Latin word 'media,' which means 'medium' or 'intermediary,' more specifically referring to 'mass media.' Media serves to enrich the process of lifelong learning with visual materials, enhancing the quality of lessons and the effectiveness of student learning.

Media literacy is the ability of learners to engage with information disseminated through mass media, to select, sort, analyze, and evaluate it based on their knowledge, and to use it appropriately in their professional activities.

Independent activity is an active educational process that allows learners to reinforce their ICT competencies in academic activities, acquire new knowledge independently, and apply the knowledge gained in their professional activities.

In the conducted research, discussions arose regarding the main tasks and characteristics of concepts related to media literacy, media competence, and media education. In this regard, we identified the following key tasks of these concepts: teaching media education based on media. It represents an educational process that helps understand the fundamental laws of media and is aimed at developing skills in receiving, studying, and analyzing media; using media to acquire and develop materials, resources, knowledge, and skills in media education; media competence is the knowledge, skills, and abilities taught during the learning process, and the capacity to creatively apply them in practical activities [5].

If the didactic tools in mass media that convey knowledge serve to collect media information for the teacher, as well as for the assimilation and direction of theoretical, practical, and independent learning materials for the student, they act as instruments for independent and creative thinking, critical perception, and evaluation of information for the learner. The didactic stages of media literacy are as follows:

1. The educational goal (learning, study, professional competence) consists of the professional competencies that learners must acquire during the development of academic activities using media tools and resources.
2. The educational function (curriculum planning, educational orientation, assessment) consists of the professional competencies that learners must acquire during the development of academic activities using media tools and resources.
3. Educational content (teaching methods, tools, forms) consists of educational methods, forms, and tools aimed at developing informational competencies through media literacy.

Based on the conducted analysis, we identified the following key features of organizing independent learning activities for students through media literacy in education: the motives for independent learning activities; the use of media technologies and the correct selection of information when organizing independent activities; searching for necessary academic materials for study; the emergence of the need for independent learning, self-assessment, awareness of the need for knowledge, and goal-setting; acquiring theoretical knowledge; the ability to generalize the obtained results and apply them in professional activities.

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